

**PECULIARITIES OF THE CONCEPTS OF INTANGIBLE BENEFITS
AND PERSONAL NON-PROPERTY RIGHTS IN CIVIL LEGISLATION**

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Abstract:

This article analyzes the legal nature of intangible benefits and personal non-property rights within civil legislation, as well as their interrelation and distinctive features in legal regulation. Intangible benefits are associated with a person's natural and social existence, and their legal protection is ensured through personal non-property rights. The article highlights the place and significance of these rights within the civil law system, drawing attention to the pressing issues arising in the process of their implementation.

Keywords: Civil law, intangible benefits, personal non-property rights, honor and dignity, personal inviolability, image, moral damage, legal protection, legal regulation.

Today, as special attention is being paid to the modernization and reform of our country and the formation of civil society institutions, the large-scale reforms being implemented in Uzbekistan are directly linked to ensuring the well-being of citizens and the realization and protection of their rights and legitimate interests. As noted by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, *"Ensuring fundamental human rights and freedoms occupies a central place in the reforms underway in Uzbekistan. The Sustainable Development Goals set for 2030 will be implemented on the basis of the principle*

of 'leaving no one behind,' which envisages guaranteeing the rights and legitimate interests of every person in our country."

A defining feature of any democratic society is the recognition and guarantee of human rights and freedoms. In Uzbekistan, the legal reforms carried out in recent years are particularly significant for their focus on upholding human dignity and ensuring the protection and implementation of personal non-property rights.

For instance, Article 26 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan states: *"The dignity and honor of the individual are inviolable. Nothing may serve as a basis for their discrimination."* The fact that the Constitution and other normative acts define the individual as the highest value, and enshrine norms related to human honor and dignity, demonstrates the high level of attention being given at the state level to personal non-property relations.

One of the key features of a modern civil society is the recognition of an individual's personal intangible (non-property) rights and the effective legal protection of those rights. Various types of personal non-property rights are legally enshrined in the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Civil Code, and a number of sectoral legislative acts. These rights not only ensure the protection of human dignity, personal inviolability, and reputation, but also create a legal foundation for individuals to fully develop their personality and freely express themselves in society.

Although the primary function of civil law is to regulate property relations, it also plays a significant role in governing relations that are not related to material wealth but rather to the personality of the individual — that is, personal non-property relations. These relations are connected with an individual's dignity, freedom, honor, personal inviolability, and other moral values, and are subject to legal protection.

In civil law, the issue of the classification of intangible benefits and personal non-property rights has been comprehensively and extensively

analyzed. The Civil Code does not provide a specific classification of intangible benefits and personal non-property rights. However, legal literature pays considerable attention to the classification of these categories. According to scholarly sources, intangible benefits and personal non-property rights are generally classified into:

1. benefits and rights that ensure a person's physical integrity,
2. benefits and rights that ensure social well-being, and
3. benefits and rights that guarantee personal autonomy within society.

In addition, it is important to note that many scholars have proposed alternative bases for the classification of intangible benefits and personal non-property rights. In particular, the works of Sh.T. Tog'aynazorov, A. Khasanov, and A. Niyazova provide a range of criteria and corresponding types for classifying personal non-property rights.

Based on these considerations, the grounds for the emergence of intangible benefits and personal non-property rights can be divided into two main groups:

1. intangible benefits and personal non-property rights that belong to a person from birth, and
2. those that arise in accordance with the law.

The first group includes such benefits as health, the inviolability of private life, name, and similar rights that are inherently linked to the individual from the moment of birth. The second group comprises intangible benefits such as scientific works, literary and artistic creations, and other outcomes of intellectual activity. These are considered as the objective results of the author's intellectual and creative efforts.

As Uzbekistan shifts toward an innovation-based development path and ensures sustainable economic growth through effective utilization of the results of scientific and technical activities, L.Kh. Tashpulatova rightly emphasizes the

necessity to improve legislation on intellectual property. This includes the need for clear and precise legal regulation of relations related to the creation and use of intellectual property objects, as well as the improvement of tax legislation to stimulate the development and commercial use of scientific and technical outcomes for public needs.

According to I. Nasriyev, the classification of personal non-property rights can be approached both generally and specifically. From this, the following conclusions can be drawn: **Firstly**, personal non-property rights protected by civil law should be classified according to the branch of law. In such classification, personal non-property rights arising from labor, family, administrative, or other legal relations should be excluded. However, this does not prevent the formation of a unified system of personal non-property rights that arise across all spheres of life.

Secondly, the system of personal non-property rights should be based on a unified criterion. As a classification basis, it is possible to approach the grouping of these rights from the perspective of the objectives they aim to achieve. Analysis shows that personal non-property rights can be classified according to various criteria. At the same time, it is not possible to classify all such rights strictly based on a single criterion, since such an approach would fail to reflect the full diversity of these rights.

In this regard, it is proposed to classify non-property rights according to their impact on personal non-property relations, where the object is an intangible benefit — i.e., depending on whether these rights are **regulative**, **protective**, or **defensive** in nature.

Regulative personal non-property rights govern the acquisition, exercise, and termination of rights related to intangible benefits. Accordingly, these types of rights fall into the category of regulative personal non-property rights. In our view, such rights include copyright, as a result of intellectual activity. As is well known, copyright regulates the relations connected to the use of intellectual

works and their outcomes.

Additionally, regulative personal non-property rights may also include rights that ensure a person's physical existence — such as the right to life and the right to reproduction. Moreover, rights that support an individual's social identity — such as the right to a name, the right to choose a place of residence or place of stay — can also be classified within this group.

Protective personal non-property rights safeguard intangible benefits, since the aforementioned non-property rights — considered as objects of intangible benefits — are enshrined in law. In our opinion, the following rights fall into the category of protective personal non-property rights: the right to a healthy environment, the right to the inviolability of private life, the right to privacy of personal life, the right to the inviolability of the home, the right to the confidentiality of personal documents (such as correspondence), the right to the inviolability of personal communication tools (including the secrecy of telephone conversations, written messages, and telegraph communications), the right to the inviolability of physical appearance, the right to medical confidentiality, the right to the confidentiality of notarial acts, banking secrecy, adoption secrecy, and attorney-client privilege.

We also believe that the **right to use legal mechanisms for the protection of intangible benefits** should be considered part of the category of personal non-property rights that protect such benefits. This includes the right to use legal remedies to protect life, health, name, honor, dignity, business reputation, personal freedom, and personal inviolability.

As previously noted, the regulation, management, and protection of intangible benefits are implemented through the complex interplay of norms from multiple branches of law. In legal theory, at least two different perspectives exist concerning the civil-law regulation of relationships involving intangible benefits. According to one group of scholars, civil law does not regulate these types of legal

relations but rather provides only protection.

Based on the provisions of the current Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, personal non-property relations can be divided into those that are regulated by civil legislation and those that are protected by it. When personal non-property rights are associated with property relations and are based on the equality of participants, freedom of will, and property independence, they are subject to regulation under civil legislation. As stated in Article 2, paragraph 1 of the Civil Code: *“Civil legislation determines the legal status of participants in civil relations, the grounds for the emergence of ownership rights and other property rights, rights to the results of intellectual activity, and the procedures for their exercise. It regulates contractual and other obligations, as well as other property and related personal non-property relations.”*

It is also worth noting that, according to Article 2, paragraph 4 of the Civil Code: *“Personal non-property relations not connected with property relations shall be governed by civil legislation, unless otherwise provided by law or if the nature of such relations does not require otherwise.”* As for property and personal non-property relations that are not regulated by family legislation, *“civil legislation shall apply to family relations only to the extent that it does not contradict their nature”* (Family Code, Article 6).

Uzbekistan’s legal framework ensures personal non-property rights through a comprehensive set of legal guarantees enshrined in both the Constitution and sectoral legislation. These include, first and foremost, **constitutional guarantees aimed at ensuring a decent standard of living.** This system of guarantees comprises:

- state support for low-income families and other forms of social protection for the population;

- the right not to be subjected to torture, violence, cruel or degrading treatment or punishment, and to be free from involuntary medical, scientific, or other experiments;
 - the right of private property owners to possess, use, and dispose of their property at their discretion;
 - the right to work under conditions that meet safety and hygiene requirements and for remuneration not less than the minimum wage established by law;
 - the right to rest;
 - the right to social security;
 - the right to qualified medical care, and thus to health protection and access to medical assistance;
 - the right to benefit from cultural heritage;
 - the right to a healthy environment;
- and other fundamental rights that reflect the human-centered nature of Uzbekistan's legal system.

These guarantees are clearly reflected and continuously developed in legislative acts and other legal documents that define the essence and content of specific rights, as well as in the organizational, financial, and other conditions for their implementation.

Secondly, there are legal norms that define the limits of use for tools, equipment, mechanisms, and physical force that may pose a danger to people's lives and health. In this regard, reference is made, in particular, to the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Code on Administrative Responsibility, and laws such as "On Road Traffic Safety," "On the Safety of Hydraulic Structures," "On Urban Passenger Transport," "On Radiation Safety," "On Automobile Roads," "On Railway Transport," "On Motor Transport," and other regulatory legal acts.

Actions that cause harm or pose a risk of harm to human life and health fall

into a third group, for which liability measures have been established. Most of these measures are provided for in the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In particular, it prescribes liability for intentional homicide, intentional infliction of serious bodily harm, failure to assist a person whose life or health is in danger and who is unable to protect themselves, and for endangering not only specific individuals but also the population of a country, region, or certain area through criminal acts.

It should be emphasized that in the classification of personal non-property rights, the guarantees that ensure the realization of other rights are no less significant.

In conclusion, personal non-property rights constitute the spiritual (non-material) wealth of a person in civil law. They serve as the legal foundation for a person's free development, maturity, and equal participation in social relations as a legal subject. The effective protection of these rights can only be achieved through proper legal regulation, strong legal mechanisms, and the application of practical legal culture.

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